

NFDI4Biodiversity Training and Education

Through supporting exceptional competencies in data management, collaborating with stakeholders, and promoting awareness, our training and education activities drive a cultural change for more effective data management in biodiversity research, adhering to the principles of good scientific practice.

Sustainable Structures

The training coordinator oversees training activities, governed by the Steering Committee and SIG3 Training. Strategic collaborations with external organisations, create synergies and effective marketing strategies enhance the visibility and attractiveness of training offers and materials.

Available Training Offers

The NFDI4Biodiversity partner organisations jointly provide a comprehensive, needs-based, modular, and scalable training portfolio for researchers, students, and data scientists. It includes various training formats combining generic Research Data Management (RDM) skills with domain-specific topics. To aid educators in integrating data literacy and RDM into university curricula, Open Educational Resources (OER) are provided for integration into lectures.

Implementation and Utilisation

In the last three years (2020- 2023), we have organised over 40 lectures and workshops with more than 800 participants. These events, tailored to specific topics, skill levels, user categories, and data types, have enriched our training portfolio in five training modules (see Figure). Our collaborative endeavors with service providers and partner institutions, through Task Areas (TA) and Measures (M), have successfully brought these offerings to life.

Impact on Partner Institutions

The training activities address specific challenges, such as legal aspects, and common training events like the Winter School 2022, foster collaboration, networking, and the integration of diverse perspectives and expertise. NFDI4Biodiversity training events and materials integrate partner data and various tools and services e.g. BEXIS2, BIIGLE, DMP Tool, Data Submission Service, DWB, RightField, VAT.

Quality of Services

The NFDI4Biodiversity quality management follows best practices of relevant initiatives such as Hessian Research Data Infrastructures (HeFDI) and German Initiative for Network Information (DINI). Continuous quality control, user feedback, and performance reviews ensure the training is tailored, well-defined, and meets community standards.